
EXAMINING THE SCALE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY APPLICATION TO LAND ADMINISTRATION IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA

BY

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ABSTRACT

This study is an attempt at assessing the degree to which digital technology application to land administration in South East Nigeria comply with current global best practices seen as present global standards in land administration. The study anchored on the critical relevance of land administration to sustainable development, the place of digital technology in defining current global best practices in land administration and the reality that local and national practices that significantly fall short of global standards are no longer acceptable in today's world that has turned into a global village. Critical areas of digital technology application to land administration on current global best practices were identified and used to assess the degree to which the five states of south east Nigeria complied. Survey method was adopted in the study, basically using the instrument of questionnaire. Purposive sampling technique was used with sample size of 150 respondents involved, who were land administration service providers comprising land officers, land surveyors, town planners and other support staff of the government ministries in charge of land administration in the states. Findings from the study revealed that the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states of south east Nigeria is significantly low and that the extent of the challenges that emanate from such low application is significantly high. The study concludes and recommends that there is an urgent need for the states to migrate swiftly to Digital Land Administration System (DLAS) by adopting a holistic digital technology application to land administration in order to be on the level of current global best practices that can drastically address land administration challenges in the states.

KEY WORDS: Land, land administration, digital technology application, global best practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Land administration undoubtedly stands out as a key driver of development based on the pivotal place occupied by land in the life of man and human activities. Land is often regarded as the single most important asset which can be possessed by an individual, an organization, a family, a community, a state or a nation. The reason for this is not far-fetched. It provides the base for shelter (a basic need of man), base for food production (another basic need of man), and base for production of clothing (yet another basic need of man). Even security which has also established itself as a basic need of man, has requirement for land. In fact, there is hardly any sector of the economy of a nation that has no requirement for land. Highlighting on the place of land in the life of man and nations, Umeh (1973) holds that land is a fundamental necessity of life and the very foundation and framework on and within which social, political and economic activities of a nation function. Similarly, Adeniyi (2015) asserts that land is the ultimate and most basic resource on which the wealth of a nation and the continued existence of the population rest. Therefore, any nation that understands the focal position of land in her overall wealth and economy can never joke with the issue of land administration.

Land administration is basically the act of direction and supervision of public and private interests and objectives in land ownership and use, usually aimed at achieving a secure, harmonious, and peaceful public and private productive efforts in land ownership and use. Interestingly, the relevance of land administration to sustainable development has been acknowledged for over two decades. Towards the end of the 20th century, the Bathurst Declaration (1999) identified and recognized the nexus between land administration and sustainable development, acknowledging the potential influence and relevance of land administration to dictate the pace of development for humankind.

Notably, the term “sustainable development” is a development concept defined by the UN’s Brundtland Commission (1987) as “development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. Although sustainable development was fundamentally enunciated to stand on economic, social, and environmental factors as the three pillars of sustainability, the phenomenal growth in the application of digital technology to virtually every sector of human activity in the current 21st Century has brought technology as a new fourth pillar of development sustainability. Thus, digital technology is now the fourth pillar of development sustainability (Velpuri and Stendler, 2009).

With the critical position occupied by land in the life of people and nations as well as the reality that digital technology is now defining global best practices in land administration, local and national practices that fall short of global best practices are no longer fashionable in the current global village. Defining best practices, DevX (2024) refers to it as “a method or technique that is accepted as superior because it produces results that are better than those achieved by other means,” representing “the most efficient and effective way of accomplishing a task.” Hence, global best practices in land administration could be regarded as the approaches or methods that are globally considered as the standards that represent the most efficient and effective ways of land governance.

As a matter of critical desire, land governance in every clime needs to be designed to serve the four basic functions of land administration, identified by Enemark (2009) as control of land tenure, land value, land use, and land development. These basic functions are the driving

force for allocation and control of property rights, use restrictions, and use responsibilities upon which global best practices in land administration rest on having appropriate principles and practices that protect land rights and permit those rights to be used and traded efficiently and effectively in terms of simplicity, fastness, security, and minimal cost (Enermark, 2009; Williamson, 2000).

As things stand now, for a nation or state to be on current global best practices in land administration, the application of Digital Technology (DT) has become inevitable since the traditional analog approaches no longer have the capacity to drive and satisfy the demands of the 21st-century world. DT application is simply about the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) which involves deployment of internet and computer devices in doing things.

However, in Nigeria, it appears that this global new paradigm is yet to be fully embraced in land administration. The traditional analogue approach have been observed to still remain dominant, particularly in the five states of south-east Nigeria. It is this observation that stimulated interest in conducting this study. The five states of south-east Nigeria, apart from being in the same geographical area of the country, have common history of having root in the defunct Eastern Region and the defunct East Central State of Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- i. To assess the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states of South-East Nigeria vis-à-vis current global best practices;
- ii. To ascertain the extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states.

1.3 Justification for the Study

The significance of this study lies on the need for land in virtually all human activities, making it occupy a pivotal position as the bedrock of the economy and life of every nation. Therefore, land administration serves as the soul and heart of good land governance for optimization of land economy in a nation. Based on the pervasiveness of DT application to virtually every field of life as the new paradigm in the 21st-century world, the need for study of its application to land administration becomes inevitable.

1.4 The Study Area

The study area is the South East geopolitical zone of Nigeria made up of the five states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. Figure 1 is the Map of Nigeria showing the six geopolitical zones of the country, with the South East painted red.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing the six Geopolitical Zones of the country, including South East.

Source: Department of Surveying and Geo-informatics, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (2024)

Figure 2: Map showing the five states of the South East, Nigeria

Source: Department of Surveying and Geo-informatics, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (2024)

11 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 The Concepts of Land

There are different perspectives from which land is seen. These different perspectives form what has been developed as the concepts of land. Over the years, six concepts of land have been identified and enunciated by (Umeh, 1967; Ogbuefi, 2001; Egolum, 2002). These six concepts include the physical, economic, legal, socio-political, spiritual, and abstract concepts. Some scholars have now extended to seven concepts by carving out from the legal concept what they identify as a statutory concept based on the statutory exclusion of minerals as part of land in Nigeria (Emoh and Nwachukwu, 2016).

The physical concept sees land as the earth's crust (ie, the physical land), including the ground with the soil and rock, together with the permanent attachments. The economic concept looks at land as a factor of production, which personifies wealth in society. From the legal view point, land is seen as the earth's crust with its ground, what is under the ground and above the ground, including the soil, the rock, and all the natural or manmade things permanently attached thereto. From the perspective of socio-political concept, land is viewed as a territory or territorial division over which people have control, as in the case of a community, a nation, or a socio-political entity. On the other hand, the spiritual concept views land from the religious perspective as obtainable in many African traditional societies, where land is seen as having a spiritual connection with the deity, who has spiritual ownership of it. Finally, the abstract concept derives principally from the interplay of the physical and legal concepts by seeing land in terms of rights and interests in and over the use

of the physical earth, which gives power of proprietary or management control, that is, proprietary interest.

2.2 Land Administration as Driver of Land Policy.

The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE, 1996) defined land administration *as the process of determining, recording, and disseminating information about ownership, value, and use of land and its associated resources*. It essentially entails the direction, control, and supervision of land ownership rights and use to achieve desired objectives. Its overall goal is fundamentally to drive the articulation and implementation of land policy. Land administration presupposes that the state or government takes responsibility for overseeing and ensuring that the land resources within her geographical jurisdiction are administered and managed in the manner that protects people's land rights, investments, and developmental efforts (Agwubike, 2021). One thing that has been found to be critical in the operation of land administration is land registration

2.3 Land Registration as the Cornerstone of Land Administration

In land administration, land registration is arguably the central thing around which other things revolve. It is the nucleus, the center of gravity. Without land registration, land administration becomes hollow and of no functional use (Agwubike, 2021). It may be regarded as a system by which all matters evidencing or affecting ownership, title, rights, and interests in and over land are recorded in a legally backed register to serve as protection and security of land title, rights, and interests, as well as serve as an information bureau in facilitation and support of land market transactions. Through a system of land register maintained under land registration, a record is kept on every parcel of land. Depending on the design of the register, recording may cover matters of ownership, location and site, size and shape, ownership type as to rights/interests held, development status and value, and other sundry matters affecting the land, including any judicial decision (Onyike, 2016; Agwubike, 2021). The register is usually established and operated by the Government.

The benefits of land registration are many and may include proof of ownership of land, priority ranking in settlement of dispute, support of land market for easy transfer of title, security of registered interests, safe keeping of document as certified true copy may obtained in case of loss of original document, and facilitation of compensation claim upon compulsory acquisition of land or environmental damage. Others are facilitation of mortgage loan operation, notice to the whole world on interest in land, simplicity and certainty of interest held during title search, improvement in market value, and a facilitator in dispute resolution (UNECE, 1996; Agwubike, 2021).

2.4 The Concept of Digital Technology

Digital Technology (DT), also known as Information and Communication Technology (ICT) *“refers to electronic tools, devices and systems that process, transmit and store data in binary form. Unlike analog technology which carries data in wavelength signals, digital technology encodes data as true or false, on or off. It encompasses all the systems and devices that encode and use the binary number system to represent data. These devices range from digital watches and televisions to cutting-edge robotics and artificial intelligence”* (Berman, 2021). Simply, it represents technology that relies on the use of microprocessors in form of computers and other applications that are dependent on computers such as the internet and other devices like video cameras and mobile phones, operating mainly as wireless network with increasing sophistication in application through configuration of hardware and software to achieve greater capacity and speed in receiving, storing,

transmitting and displaying larger amount and variety of data for various uses (Agwubike, 2021).

2.5 Digital Technology as Driver of Best Practices in Land Administration

There is no doubt that the application of digital technology to every sector of human endeavour has experienced phenomenal growth in the 21st century. It has become the new paradigm that touches on every sector of human works of life, including land administration. DT has therefore become the current driver of global best practices in land administration and Ezealigo (2023) notes the key goals of DT to be simplify the process, increase efficiency and ultimately produce greater user satisfaction in service delivery. On this, Onuora (2023), advises that the strategies for implementation of digital technology solutions for achievement of best practices are to: (i) research and select the right technology and technology service providers; (ii) create and develop a detailed implementation plan; (iii) invest in comprehensive training programs for staffs; (iv) foster a culture of change and innovation, communicating and inculcating in the staff the goals and benefits of integrating technology solutions; and, (v) consider regulatory and legal frameworks to ensure that the chosen solutions comply with relevant regulations, data protection laws, and security standards.

2.6 Empirical Review

2.6.1 Degree of Digital Technology Application to Land Administration in South East Nigeria

Studies have shown that no country can be on land administration's current global best practices without digital technology application (Enemark, 2009; Williamson, 2000; Vos, 2010; Gyula, 2020; Mihigo and Magina, 2022; and UNECE, 2023). Unfortunately, it seems there have not been much studies conducted in Nigeria that clearly showed the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states of South East Nigeria in relation to global best practices. However, there are some studies that are suggestive that the degree is low, including studies conducted by Umeokafor (2010); Nigeria's PTCLR (2014); Ghebru and Okumo (2017); Nwokike (2019); and Ugonabo, Igwe, and Oladejo (2018).

The low degree of awareness and skill regarding the application of digital technology to land administration in Nigeria came on focus in the study by Umeokafor, (2010) which was on *Review of Land Information Management in Enugu and Anambra States and the Potentials of GIS in Improving Land Information Management in the States*. The study was approached by use of survey method and applied sampling technique. The study sampled thirty-one (31) land officers in Enugu State and nineteen (19) land officers in Anambra State. It further sampled twenty-five (25) Estate Surveyors and twenty-five (25) Lawyers in both states. The result showed that as high as eighty-one percent (81%) of the respondents had only little knowledge of the use of computer, resulting to land information substantially being managed by analogue approach in the two states, even as comparatively Anambra State was found to have a little edge over Enugu State in transition to digital technology.

Following observable high extent of gaps from global best practices, the Federal Government of Nigeria in 2009 established a Presidential Technical Committee on Land Reform (PTCLR). The Committee conducted study on land administration in the country after which it observed a number of inadequacies of near to a chaotic situation in land administration in the country. As a solution, it came up with a proposal for the country to adopt what it called "Systematic Land Titling and Registration (SLTR)" (PTCLR, 2014). The SLTR was built by the Committee within the context of the country's Land Use Act (LUA) of 1978 which has

remained in force as the principal land policy document in Nigeria till date. This seems to be what was intended as the country's Fit-For-Purpose approach, designed to suit and fit the needs in Nigeria within the ambits of the peoples changing social systems, existing laws, and economic developmental demands. The PTCLR (2014) on digital technology application component of the Nigerian land reform proposal, looked into the earlier attempts by state governments and observed that these attempts by the governments of some States to address the continued challenges in land registration "have always been equated to mean the computerization of the registration process without more". The PTCLR hence moved to adopt some digital technological software packages for application in land registration in Nigeria with regard to administration of the proposed regulations in furtherance of the LUA and SLTR. The name which the PTCLR called the major technology software recommended for adoption in Nigeria for SLTR is "Solutions for Open Land Administration" with "SOLA" as the acronym.

An observed shortcoming here is that there was not been effective co-ordination in forging a common front between the Federal Government and State Governments to actualize the reform as regards the regulations and the digital technology applications. This is a serious drawback because much more of land administration in Nigeria is under the control of the States within the provisions of the LUA. Success can therefore be made only where the states buy into the concept and approach, under effective leadership of the central government of the federation. Again, as pointed out by Ugonabo (2002), the PTCLR was envisaged to be a body that would later transform to a National Land Reform Commission that would oversee land sector reform and monitor the reform process and performance. However, with the current look of things on ground, this envisaged transformation is yet to be seen in reality, and the reform appears to be in comatose since the end of the political leadership that gave birth to the child, that is, the administration of Dr. Goodluck Jonathan whose leadership as President of Nigeria ended in 2015.

Focusing on the nature of land administration challenges and service delivery in Nigeria, Ghebru and Okumo (2017) conducted study on *Land Administration Service Delivery and its Challenges in Nigeria*. The study, approached from survey method, used data collected from three sets of participants in land administration process. The three classes of participants used were: 1) service-providers who were land administration officials (76), 2) land beneficiaries who were service users (253), and 3) land service professionals (172). The data were collected from the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja) and seven states selected from the six geopolitical zones of the country, namely: Cross River (South-South), Benue (North-Central), Bauchi (North-East), Enugu (South-East), Kaduna (North-West), and Lagos and Ekiti (South-West). The findings showed that close to 80 percent of beneficiaries and 41 percent of professionals responded that it took more than two years to complete the process of land registration from the time of application commencement to completion. This difference between beneficiaries and professionals may stem from the fact that many professionals, who generally are better educated, may know more about the application process than do beneficiaries and are able to navigate the process more efficiently. The study also revealed that information guidelines on land registration were not readily available to the public since the dominant means of access to land administration institutions and information is through direct contact. It became self-evident from the study's revelation that there was total or substantial non employment of digital technology to land administration in the studied areas. The study, conducted about seven years ago, selected only Enugu State and used it to generalize for the South East Nigeria without due regard to the fact that each state may have its own local peculiarities.

In another study by Ugonabo, Igwe, and Oladejo (2018) the focus was on the *Impact of Land Administration on Housing Delivery in Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria*. The study aimed at examining the impact of lack of effective land administration on housing delivery in the commercial city of Onitsha with a view to developing efficient land administration policy to enhance housing delivery in the city. Specific objectives were to: show the nexus between land administration and housing delivery; examine the extent to which inefficient land administration hinders housing delivery; and determine the rationale behind the growing trend of investors' shifting away from housing development in Onitsha. The study adopted a survey approach, using sampling technique. Respondents to the study were drawn from a sample of residential property investors (385) and real estate professionals (36) in Onitsha. Very significant among the findings was that ineffective land administration is a principal factor that resulted in steady decline in housing delivery in Onitsha, from 99% in 2004 to 29% in 2010, being a huge 70% drop within the 7-year period covered by the study. The revelation of delay in processing land registration, high cost of land titling and registration, and analogue approach to land administration were found to be part and parcel of the ineffective land administration contributing to the worsening degree of housing deficit in the city. The observed limitation of this study is that it was never intended to cover south east Nigeria but focused on only one city in Anambra State.

2.6.2 Challenges Emanating from the Degree of DT Application to LA in the States

From the foregoing empirical studies indicating seemingly low degree of digital technology application to land administration in South-East Nigeria in relation to global best practices, multifarious challenges emanate. This has been evidenced by results from studies conducted by a number of scholars and researchers, including studies by: Ghebru and Okumo (2017); and Azie, Egolum and Ugonabo (2022).

The study by Ghebru and Okumo (2017) earlier presented here on “land administration service delivery and its challenges in Nigeria” revealed not only the low the degree of digital technology application to land administration in south east Nigeria vis-a-vis global best practices but also that there are many challenges that result from such low degree of digital technology application to land administration, with the challenge of inefficiency being pointed out conspicuously.

On their part, Azie, Egolum and Ugonabo (2022) focused their study on the “Effect of Geographic Information System on Urban Land Administration in Enugu, Nigeria”. The study was stimulated by numerous indications suggesting that the goals of land administration were bedeviled by inefficiencies such as title document duplicity, delayed processes and ineffective land use monitoring. The study was meant to check the application of GIS tool for land administration in Enugu State. Descriptive research design was employed over a population of 411 employees of the Enugu State Ministry in charge of land administration. Given the manageable nature of the population, a census study was conducted, with data collected using structured questionnaire, and analyzed by use of Spearman Rank Order Correlation. Findings showed significant positive correlations between ArcGIS data management and duplicity attenuation ($r=.928$; $p<.01$), data efficiency and customer responsiveness ($r=.937$; $p<.01$) and remote sensing data capture and land use monitoring for sustainability in the study area ($r=.790$; $p<.01$). The study concluded that GIS has significant positive effect on urban land administration in Enugu State. As a result, the study recommended recruitment and training in requisite ArcGIS, Geomedia and remote sensing competencies by the Ministry as a way of addressing the challenges of inefficiency manifested in duplicity of title documents, delayed process and ineffective land use

monitoring. One limitation that the study has that it focused to only Enugu State without extending to the other states in South-East Nigeria.

111 METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study using the survey research method. The study population of interest was those that provide land administration services in the states of south east Nigeria. They are the officers of the Department of Lands, Department of Survey extending to Office of the Surveyor General, Department of Town Planning, Department of Finance/Revenue & Accounts, and Department of Administration, Research and Statistical Planning. The officers in these departments of the relevant ministry in charge of land administration in each of the five states of the study area constituted the target population for the study. With this, the target population of the study was 1,779 from which a sample size of 327 was determined using Taro Yamani formula. The research instrument for data collection was questionnaire structured in Likert Scale format. Data were analyzed with Analysis of Variance Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Analysis

This study analyzed data obtained from the study questionnaire. A total of three hundred and twenty seven (327) copies of the questionnaire were distributed in accordance with the study sample population sector of each state, out of which three hundred and nine (309) were fully completed and returned.

- **Hypothesis One:** Hypothesis one, on null hypothesis, was that: the degree of digital technology application to land administration is not significant in the states of South-East Nigeria vis-à-vis current global best practices. In data analysis, one sample t-test was used and one set of observation was compared to a standard. Decision Rule was to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, otherwise reject it. This was tested with Analysis of Variance Statistical Package and the results were as shown in the table below:

Table 1: One Sample Statistics for Degree of Digital Technology Application to Land Administration

	N	Mean	Stan. Dev.	Stan. Error Mean
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Abia State	110	4.2286	.17002	.01621
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Anambra State	49	2.7726	.17956	.02565
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Ebonyi State	13	1.4286	.34503	.09569
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Enugu State	92	1.9332	.26320	.02744
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Imo State	46	1.8913	.21335	.03146

Table 2: One Sample Test for Degree of Digital Technology Application to Land Administration. Test Value = 3

	T	Dif	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Dif.	95% Confidence Interval (Lower)	95% Confidence Interval (Upper)
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Abia State	75.785	109	.000	1.22857	1.1964	1.2607
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Anambra State	-8.865	48	.000	-.22741	-.2790	-.1758
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Ebonyi State	-16.421	12	.000	-1.57143	-1.7799	-1.3629
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Enugu State	-38.875	91	.000	-1.06677	-1.1213	-1.0123
The degree of digital technology application to land administration in Imo State	-35.245	45	.000	-1.10870	-1.1721	-1.0453

It can be seen that the p-values for all the states are each 0.000, all less than 0.05, Abia State excepted. This implies that the degree of digital technology application to land administration in all the states is significantly low except that of Abia state where it is significantly high.

- **Hypothesis Two:** Hypothesis two, also on null hypothesis, was that: the extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states is not significant. One-sample t-test was used and a set of observations was compared to a standard. Also here, the decision rule was to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, otherwise reject it.

Table 3: One-Sample Statistics for Extent of Challenges that result from the Degree of Digital Technology Application to Land Administration

	N	Mean	Stan. Dev.	Stan. Error Mean
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Abia State	110	1.8532	.14411	.01374
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Anambra State	49	2.9213	.17990	.02570
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Ebonyi State	13	4.8791	.11438	.03172
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Enugu State	92	3.8370	.13820	.01441
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Imo State	46	4.3106	.25252	.03723

Table 4: One-Sample Test for Extent of Challenges that result from the Degree of Digital Technology Application to Land Administration. Test Value = 3.

	T	Dif	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Dif.	95% Confidence Interval (Lower)	95% Confidence Interval (Upper)
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Abia State	-83.460	109	.000	-1.14675	-1.1740	-1.1195
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Anambra State	-3.063	48	.000	-.07872	-.1304	-.0270
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Ebonyi State	59.236	12	.000	1.87912	1.8100	1.9482
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Enugu State	58.088	91	.000	.83696	.8083	.8656
Extent of challenges that result from the degree of digital technology application to land administration in Imo State	35.199	45	.000	1.31056	1.2356	1.3855

From Table 4, it can be seen that p-values of the test are all 0.000, which are less than 0.05. The implication being that the extent of challenges that result the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states is significant. It is significantly high in all the states except Abia State where it is significantly low.

4.2 Discussion of Results

From the results of the postulated two hypotheses, we discover firstly that the degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states of south-east Nigeria is significantly low, with the exception of Abia State where it is significantly high and secondly that the extent of challenges that emanate from the low degree of digital technology application to land administration in the states is significantly high, except for Abia State where the extent of challenges is significantly low. One observes here that where the degree of digital technology application is low, the extent land administration challenges become high and vice versa.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that with the general low degree of DT application to land administration in south-east Nigeria against global best practices and the high extent of land administration challenges that result from the low degree DT application to land administration in the area, it is now a necessity for every state in the South East geopolitical region of Nigeria to urgently reform her land administration practice through the application of digital technology to land administration. The crying need now in the study area is for rapid incremental replacement of the traditional analogue system with a Fit-For-Purpose (FFP) Digital Land Administration System (DLAS). The conclusive truth is that under the current global reality, DLAS is the only land administration practice with limitless capacity and capability that can make each state to be on the current global standards in land administration.

Corollary, it is recommend that each state in south-east Nigeria should adopt and prioritize her own Fit-For-Purpose Digital Land Administration System (FFP-DLAS) in order to come up to the level of global best practices in land administration for efficient and effective service delivery.

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